

Relationships, Participation and Art Ritual: The Art Practice of Yuval Avital

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The idea that cultural and social dimensions are inherently interconnected is not a novel concept. Over the past few decades, there has been frequent discussion about the "democratization of culture" and how artistic expression serves as an interpretation of contemporary society. This contribution has activated processes that have, in turn, given rise to various forms of communication, fostering the much-anticipated transformation of the collective experience.

The research conducted by artist and composer Yuval Avital (born in Jerusalem in 1977) is an integral part of this ongoing process, deeply rooted in the human experience, both in terms of introspection and connection to the external world. Avital embarks on a continual exploration of his inner self, connecting with the deepest recesses of the soul, the very core of our thoughts. Themes such as sanctity and carnality, identity and instinct, fear and desire, light and darkness, dreams and affections are consistently prevalent in Yuval Avital's art. These elements play a profound role in shaping our innermost being. Avital strongly believes in the participatory role of art, not only from a moral standpoint but also due to its potent aesthetic potential. According to the artist, this process is rooted deeply within every human being, resonating like a membrane. This means that anyone can partake in artistic creation without the need for special education or background, solely through

a profound exploration of the unconscious. This forms the foundation of his art—an immersive and profound expression that rejects mere imitation or the replication of precise patterns in favor of listening to and giving voice to the individual's experience, which then becomes a shared experience, stirring the universal subconscious.

HUMAN SIGNS is a global work of gesture and voice conceived by multimedia artist Yuval Avital in collaboration with Stefania Ballone, a dancer and choreographer at Teatro alla Scala. It stands as an artistic anomaly, not produced or commissioned by external entities but driven by the authors themselves. Specifically, it was the conditions of solitude, stillness, and introspection brought about by the COVID-19 epidemic that inspired them to conceive this collective project.

Yuval Avital, HUMAN SIGNS - Ensemble n.5, 2021

Born during isolation, reflecting the unique aesthetic of this moment in history, HUMAN SIGNS explores the diverse relationships we developed during months of confinement—alterations in our perception of our bodies, obsessive interactions with technology, virtual communities, collective and individual experiences. The concept of a boundary is typically understood as a real

or imaginary line that demarcates the limits of a territory, separating it from its neighbors. However, in the case of HUMAN SIGNS, this term is inverted and envisioned as a permeable threshold where everything converges. The project begins with Avital's personal testimony—a 12-minute self-filmed reflection during confinement, where the artist delves into his innermost thoughts. The result is a mantra that, echoing the aesthetics of the virus, travels worldwide via the internet to enter the homes of artists, inviting them to respond through voice and gesture—two fundamental forms of human expression. Expanding from the virtual realm, the project also encompasses physical and experiential dimensions, including exhibitions and live performances. By fostering a profound sense of togetherness, HUMAN SIGNS aims to transcend physical distance and isolation, encouraging us to perceive spaces, languages, and forms of interconnectedness differently. It prompts us to reconsider these elements as part of a collective reflection on a period that has felt stagnant.

HUMAN SIGNS stands as a testament to our contemporary era, a manifestation born in the present—a work of both ethical and aesthetic significance that remains open and continually evolving.

The concept of art as a public call aligns with the artist's aspiration to foster connections and initiate a transformative endeavor that unveils what has been concealed. The power of Avital's participatory works, such as *Variations on Harmonic Tremor*, lies in their capacity to establish profound and dynamic relationships with communities and individuals. This expansive artwork extends beyond being a mere tool for communication and dialogue with the public. Instead, it takes the form of genuine moments of co-creation, exchange, and enlightenment—not only regarding the culture and society

Yuval Avital, *Variations on Harmonic Tremor*, installation view, Leonardo da Vinci National Museum of Science and Technology, Milan, 2017
Photo: Michela Albert

of its time but also with respect to the language and structure of the contemporary art realm.

Within this artwork, hundreds of voices, faces, flowing lava, billowing steam, musical bands, and tambourines, as well as ancient dialectal expressions and human clusters, are condensed into an immense allegorical tableau that traverses a distinctive landscape. This tableau is the outcome of a meticulous exploration of the unique cultural and natural environment surrounding Mount Etna, the largest active volcano in Europe.

The term "harmonic tremor" signifies a physical-acoustic phenomenon that frequently accompanies volcanic activity, often manifesting itself through the release of seismic or infrasonic energy—sounds too low in frequency for the human ear to perceive. Etna's harmonic tremor, with its inaudible but perceptible music to human senses, at times evoking extreme and contrasting emotional states such as awe, harmony, disquiet, or revelation, serves as the thematic thread running through the multimedia artist and composer Yuval Avital's investigative journey. This journey culminated in a solo exhibition at the Leonardo da Vinci National Museum of Science and Technology in Milan in November 2017. The exhibition comprised over 400 photographs, a newly created sound sculpture, various pieces of video art, and a sound and visual polyptych featuring more than 75 scenes involving over 350 participants who responded to a public call for involvement.

Yuval Avital's analysis delves into the relationship between the completed work and the process of its creation. It is within this realm that the synthesis of his artistic endeavors is truly comprehended, transcending temporal and stylistic categorizations. It is here that the intricate connections between idea, project, space, image,

structure, technology, and human relationships come to light.

In 2019, a remarkable project named URLA was born as the centerpiece of the Open Sound Festival in Matera, designated as the European Capital of Culture. URLA involved the composition of a musical score for over three hundred musicians, blending traditional and contemporary talents from the Basilicata region, along with electronic and theatrical elements.

Yuval Avital, URLA,
Matera European
Capital Culture,
2019

Photo: Francesca
Petretti

As a musician and composer, Yuval Avital's artistic exploration is drawn to the voice—an instrument that serves as a metaphor and a medium. Avital perceives the voice as a powerful vehicle for artistic expression. He recognizes that the ability to work with large groups of people carries both aesthetic and moral significance. Within an ensemble, an organizational framework emerges that enables the harmonious coexistence of multiple sonic elements. When nurtured through attentive listening and a thoughtful process, the human voice, in particular, has the potential to evolve into an

extraordinary art form. When vocal expressions are intertwined with visual representations of individuals or groups, a complex contextualization unfolds. This process accentuates a diverse array of immediate iconic details, such as the environment, posture, clothing, age, and unique characteristics. These elements combine to create comprehensive multisensory microcosms that unveil latent possibilities within a given space or community. These manifestations serve as testimonials and poetic transformations of the individuals and groups involved in the artistic process.

In contemporary society, the voice, often relegated to the periphery, is frequently muted but never entirely extinguished; it perpetually lingers within each of us. Nonetheless, there exist certain situations and places where this voice can still be heard. For quite some time, the artist has been on a quest for the rarity of words that convey authenticity, that unearth something deeply affecting, compelling the listener from their core. This pursuit has been embedded by the artist within the broader concept of the total work of art—a concept perceived from both the viewpoint of the viewer, who, amidst a deluge of stimuli, is ushered into an emotionally receptive state, and from that of the artist, who possesses the ability to materialize this amalgamation of image and sound in their museum and stage productions.

The amalgamation of relational practice with the concept of sound has given rise to the Icon-Sonic Postcards. It is within the convergence of vocal and visual expressiveness that the potential for an icon emerges—an ancient concept deeply ingrained in our culture, representing a symbol that resonates with our identity, ultimately solidifying into a tangible image. To craft an Icon-Sonic Postcard, "Virgiles" or guides are essential

to facilitate intimacy with people. Next, an iconic image is sought that allows for the definition and realization of the action through brief dialogues. Finally, digital processing of both sound and image results in a complete representation. Inspiration can spring from intricate details or something as elemental as a breath, constructing a territorial map through voice and body.

The inaugural series of *ICON SONIC POSTCARDS* in 2017 was centered in Reggio Emilia. The artist explored diverse locales in the city, including a kindergarten, Collezione Maramotti, a language center, or a dance school, aiming to capture an icono-sonic tableau initiated by the community's voices. This endeavor fashioned a collective iconography, generating a series of postcards that, while narrating the uniqueness of those spaces, could resonate in any other city. The objective was to craft an intricate image, a tableau vivant, illustrating facets of Reggio Emilia's essence, subsequently transplanting them into a broader canvas. Within this creative odyssey lies the rediscovery of people's willingness to open up, not as an act of exhibitionism but as a genuine desire to share something intimate with another soul. The work was displayed as a medley of postcards that, through the shared temporal space, gave birth to a complex relationship akin to an allegorical painting.

A year later, at the Macro Asilo in Rome, the challenge reached an unprecedented level. The aim was to undertake the second series of this project, under entirely distinct aesthetic and environmental conditions. This necessitated the artist to embark on an innovative creative process. In *POSTCARDS FROM ROME*, the diverse and eclectic voices of the city coalesced into an immense meta-chorus, enabling the recreation of a 360-degree sonic portrait of the metropolis. The project was conceived as

a process of gathering, engaging, inspiring, co-creating, and composing, utilizing a blend of different languages. Here, the role of the audience and their living environment assumed paramount importance in the emergence of territorial chorality.

The initial phase of the work deviated from the conventional artistic creation process. Instead of the artist coming to the museum, it was the city itself that entered the museum's realm. Over three hundred participants, dispersed throughout the metropolis, expressed their voices in accordance with seven visual scores devised by Yuval. He directed choirs of megaphones within the halls of the Museum of Contemporary Art in Rome. This collective polyphony, marked by the uniqueness of each voice, fostered a form of co-participation that could be described as profoundly "human" or, in Yuval Avital's own words, "truthful."

Cardinal elements were then brought to life, combining a series of coordinates linked to the participants' places of origin. Each person was encouraged to bring a handful of soil from their place of origin, symbolized by a red dot on a map. The amalgamation of these dots inspired the artist to paint on the maps, thereby creating constellations. The museum simultaneously transformed into both a set and a departure from the conventional museum concept. It became a canvas for an invasion of stories, culminating in choruses of megaphones—a tool historically associated with authority, now transformed into an instrument of beauty. Through these megaphones, the strident voices of the suburbs surfaced, reaching out to the community.

The second phase marked the actual creation of the Icon-Sonic Postcards within the urban setting. To avoid entirely departing from the museum, it was transposed into the cityscape, almost as if it were "hung" on walls, creating

new open spaces conducive to the realization of artistic rituals in the form of site-specific performances. Guided by a series of vectors, including iconic figures like the letter carrier, bartender, and greengrocer, as well as local myths and neighborhood stories, and unsung heroes, around 200 participants were coordinated and collaborated in crafting 102 postcards.

The third phase entailed the return of these 102 postcards to the Macro Asilo, accompanied by a collection of sketches, photographs, and documentation generated by students from the Academy of Fine Arts. POSTCARDS FROM ROME, as a collective endeavor, facilitated a process of re-humanization through territorial mapping. Originating from shared voices, it emphasized the inherent sense of proximity and empathy in each voice. Here, everyone was considered the "master of their own voice," an expression of their individuality, contributing to a novel conception of a global community.

Throughout these artworks, the artist's role is to arrive at a mutual understanding with the performers, leading to an exploration of a shared truth—both historical and emotional. The artist becomes an advocate for an authenticity that had long been suppressed, merely requiring the right context to emerge. In art, as in life, there are no fixed images, no immutable lines, or insurmountable boundaries; everything vibrates and is subject to change.

Yuval Avital, Postcards from Rome, process at Macro Asilo, Rome, 2018-2019